

**PILOTS for robotic Inspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

Deliverable D5.1

Beta version of advanced autonomous
functionalities for aerial robots

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Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
I&M	Inspection and Maintenance
RCS	Robot Control Station
SLAM	Simultaneous localization and mapping
UAV	Unmanned aerial vehicle
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
VIO	Visual-inertial odometry
WP	Work Package
JPS	Jump Point Search
FPFH	Fast Point Feature Histogram
RANSAC	Random Sample Consensus
ICP	Iterative Closest Point

Table 1. Acronym list.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope of the document

The main purpose of this document is to present the beta version of the algorithms developed for aerial inspection robots concerning GNSS-free navigation and aerial contact control. This deliverable is the direct outcome of the work performed within tasks T5.1 (“GNSS-free localization and navigation for aerial systems”) and T5.3 (“Aerial interaction control”) during their first period.

The envisioned scenarios for the PILOTING use cases present big challenges for the inspection and maintenance operations with aerial robots. High altitude, unstructured environments, low lighting, and lack of GNSS are just some of them. To cope with these issues, the proposed I&M Platform includes a set of autonomous functionalities which will help to safely accomplish the operations with aerial robots.

As defined in previous deliverables of this project, the autonomous functionalities for aerial robots can be summarized in five points:

- Autonomous take-off.
- Autonomous landing.
- Autonomous control while contacting the surface.
- Autonomous navigation in GNSS-denied environment.
- Autonomous obstacle detection and avoidance.

The first three functionalities are part of task T5.3 “Aerial interaction control”. The autonomous take-off and landing might seem straightforward functionalities, but one should consider the challenging conditions in which those functionalities will take place. The autonomous control while contacting the surface functionality is crucial, as it allows the aerial robots to perform the advance inspection they are designed for.

On the other hand, the autonomous navigation and obstacle detection and avoidance functionalities fall in the scope of task T5.1 “GNSS-free localization and navigation for aerial systems”. These functionalities allow the aerial robots to safely navigate the environment to reach the desired inspection locations.

1.2 Structure of the document

This document is organized as follows. Section 0 describes the general localization and navigation architecture for all the aerial robots plus the specific implementations for each of them. This section summarizes the work performed in task T5.1.

Section 0, focused on task T5.3, presents the generic dynamic model and the modular controller scheme to adapt to every aerial robot interaction control.

Finally, Section 0 presents some conclusions and future work on the described tasks.

2. GNSS-free localization and navigation for aerial systems

2.1 Introduction

Figure 1 shows the general architecture for localization and navigation for aerial systems used in this project. There are three main blocks in this architecture: perception, planning, and control. Depending on the use case, each block contains one or several algorithms running in parallel.

Figure 1: General localization and navigation architecture.

The perception block is in charge of both estimating the robot pose (position and attitude) and also increasing the situational awareness of the aerial robot, including functionalities such as detecting obstacles around, estimating the height to the landing site or estimating the distance to the surface in which it will make contact. It is the most critical one as the performance of the rest of the system depends on the accuracy of its estimations.

The planning block receives the mission from the robot control station (also known for aerial robots, ground control station or GCS). It includes the algorithms for trajectory planning and trajectory tracking, including the replanning in case of obstacle detection.

The control block oversees the interaction with the low-level control of the aerial robotic vehicle. It receives the tracking commands from the planning block, and the environmental knowledge (i.e., pose estimation, distance to the contact surface, etc.). The advanced functionalities related to this block are described in section 3 of this document.

This architecture does not constrain the type of algorithms for any of the blocks. Therefore, each different use case would need a specific implementation, depending on its particularities, the available sensors, etc. For instance, is not the same to localize a robot in the exterior part of a refinery, in the surroundings of a viaduct and below it, or inside a tunnel.

The following subsections will detail the different implementations of this architecture for each use case. Section 2.2 details the common approach for the planning. Section 2.3 focuses on localization, the main perception problem to solve. The control details are in section 3.

2.2 Planning

One of the keys to perform autonomous inspections with UAVs is trajectory planning. An autonomous UAV must be able to safely reach inspection points. Generally, inspected structures often require navigating near obstacles, so a smooth and safe trajectory between the waypoints to be inspected is necessary. For instance, scenarios such as viaducts deal with outdoor and high-altitude conditions such as wind gusts, positioning inaccuracies or being surrounded by obstacles. Thus, a trajectory planner which is able to replan, taking into account disturbances, is essential for that type of application.

Traditional path planning techniques may not be sufficient to satisfy the requirements since the path generated relies only on spatial information and may not be performed due to the dynamics of the robot or cannot consider the smoothness requirement of the application. A trajectory is a time parameterized function of robot states that contains both spatial and temporal information. Trajectories recover the full states of a dynamic system such that they are adequate to guarantee the system's feasibility, safety, and smoothness if it is required. However, since the system dynamics and time-varying states are considered, trajectory generation is computationally more demanding than path planning.

Due to the aforementioned reasons, we use an optimization-based approach using a receding horizon scheme. On the one hand, the optimization approach allows us to compute optimal trajectories minimizing accelerations and achieving smooth trajectories. On the other hand, the receding horizon approach reduces the computational demand of the optimization problem so that we can solve it at high frequency considering the disturbances mentioned above, characteristics of the inspected scenarios.

The proposed mission planner uses the architecture presented in Figure 2, where a global planner guides a horizon local planner to the desired location. The global planner used in this work is Jump Point Search (JPS). JPS finds the shortest piecewise linear path between two points in a 3D uniformly-weighted voxel grid, guaranteeing optimality and completeness but running an order of magnitude faster than A* [1]. Then, we define an optimization problem that uses the path calculated by JPS as a reference trajectory, and also, minimizes the accelerations. Figure 2 shows a diagram with the different modules of our architecture. We use ACADO¹, which is a software environment and algorithm collection for automatic control and dynamic optimization, to solve the optimization problem. The generated trajectory by ACADO is sent to the trajectory follower, which uses a pure pursuit method to properly follow the trajectory sending velocity commands to the autopilot.

¹ <https://acado.github.io/>

Figure 2: Planning architecture.

Optimization-based techniques have been used in real-time for trajectory planning such as search-based trajectory planning techniques or optimal trajectory planning techniques. As mentioned before, we use optimal trajectory planning due to the possibility of formulating convex problems that can be solved in real time using the receding horizon approach. The particular optimization task attempts to track a desired trajectory \mathbf{p}_d corresponding to the reference trajectory calculated by JPS:

$$\underset{\mathbf{u}_0, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{N-1}}{\text{minimize}} \sum_{k=1}^N \left(\|\mathbf{p}_{d,k} - \mathbf{p}_k\|^2 + \beta \|\mathbf{u}_{k-1}\|^2 \right),$$

subject to $\mathbf{x}_0 = \mathbf{x}'$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_{k+1} &= f_p(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) & \forall k \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}, \\ \mathbf{v}_{min} &\leq \mathbf{v}_k \leq \mathbf{v}_{max} & \forall k \in \{1, \dots, N\}, \\ \mathbf{u}_{min} &\leq \mathbf{u}_k \leq \mathbf{u}_{max} & \forall k \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}, \\ \mathbf{p}_k &\in \mathcal{P}_k & \forall k \in \{1, \dots, N\}, \end{aligned}$$

where $f_p(\cdot)$ represents the positional part of a dynamic model; \mathbf{v}_{min} , \mathbf{v}_{max} are velocity limitations; \mathbf{u}_{min} , \mathbf{u}_{max} , control inputs limitations.

The approach that we described above does not include the obstacles in the optimization problem. In most cases, minimizing the distance to the reference trajectory calculated by JPS is enough to avoid obstacles. However, in cluttered environments, it can lead to unsafe trajectories. In such cases, safe corridors are generated around these collision-free paths using a map of the environment represented by a point cloud. Safe corridors are generated using the convex decomposition method proposed in [1]. This method allows us to maintain the optimization problem convex, and thus, does not increase the computational cost too much.

As the viaduct case scenario can lead to difficult conditions such as wind gust at high altitude, not only do we have to ensure the generation of smooth trajectories but also that the generated trajectory is precisely followed in such conditions. The *Trajectory Follower* module (see Figure 2) is the one in charge of guaranteeing that the trajectory generated by the planner is properly followed, and hence essential for flight stability. In the presence of difficult conditions, we could use more robust UAV controllers. In our case, we implemented a trajectory follower based on a *pure pursuit* algorithm with a *look-ahead* parameter and a velocity controller. Nonetheless, alternative control techniques [2] considering external perturbations and uncertainties or integrating non-linear models for the UAV could be applied to increase flight stability in the case of wind.

Besides, in terms of trajectory planning, the weights of the cost function could also be adapted, penalizing more those costs based on UAV accelerations and relaxing the cost associated with the desired final state. Thus, the generated trajectories would be more conservative from the smoothness point of view.

2.3 Localization

Localization is one of the key functionalities to enable autonomous inspection with aerial robots. Although every inspection use case will have its specific characteristics, we can extract some common concepts and procedures that will work in any of them. In the following, these common concepts are introduced, and then, the particular implementations for each of the envisioned use cases are detailed.

In most cases, if not in all of them, a 3D map of the inspection scenario or the structure to be inspected will be available. This map could be an already existing digital twin or other specifically generated for the inspection tasks. The format of this map will be a 3D pointcloud. There are many different ways to obtain this kind of map, depending on the available sensors. In the envisioned use cases, three approaches will be considered:

- In the viaduct use cases, the map is generated by a robotic total station, a sensor typically used in civil infrastructure construction and inspection. The main feature of a total station is to accurately measure the angle and distance of specific points. Thus, it allows accurate 3D positioning of points using a prism reflector from up to 10km distance. Moreover, it can also perform precise 3D laser scanning and take digital images with an embedded camera. This sensor can generate maps with 2mm accuracy.
- In the tunnel use case, the map is generated by a 3D lidar mounted on the CART robotic vehicle. More information on this vehicle can be found in deliverable D4.1, while the mapping process is described in deliverable D5.2.
- In the refinery use cases, the map can be generated by a robotic total station if conditions permit. Given the nature of the refineries, where there are many occlusion points where the total station cannot reach, the drone itself can be used with LIDAR to

map the refinery using GPS (and RTK if available). Furthermore, for vessels and tanks, the 3D manual generation tool from the visualization portal can be used.

The map is the base of the autonomous inspection. It allows to identify the position of the defects in the structure, as well as to indicate the desired points or areas to be inspected. The map defines a global fixed reference frame linked to the infrastructure. This reference frame is time-consistent, so it allows to re-visit the same positions over and over at different times. This reference is expressed in ENU to be aligned with global coordinate systems such as GNSS.

Based on the map, all the robotic platforms should be capable of localizing themselves in the global reference frame, so they can fulfill their corresponding inspection task. This is called global localization. This global localization is achieved by different approaches such as comparing a LIDAR 3D pointcloud with the map or identifying some characteristic features in the map with other sensors like a camera. The global localization must be accurate enough to correctly perform the inspection task, sometimes sacrificing speed to reach maximum accuracy.

On the other hand, aerial robots usually need a faster localization system for a stable flight. This is called relative localization. This relative localization uses faster algorithms which may not be as accurate as the global localization ones, or they simply cannot estimate a global localization. It is relative as the localization estimation is in a local reference frame, usually placed at the takeoff or starting position. The sensors involved in these algorithms are inertial measurement units (IMUs), monocular or stereo cameras, LIDARs, etc. The typical algorithms for this relative localization are visual odometry, visual-inertial odometry (VIO), or LIDAR odometry.

Both localization systems should be somehow integrated. Here, again, there are different approaches. One can simply maintain a relative localization for the robot control while an independent global localization finds the relation (or transform) between the local and the global reference systems, so the inspection points can be translated. This global localization algorithm can also run in a ground computer receiving asynchronous petitions to estimate the aerial robot global localization. Another approach is to consider the relative localization as a first step of the global localization system, giving fast estimations while the global estimations are integrated at a lower rate. Both estimations are then fused in the same algorithm.

The next subsections detail the specific methods used for localizing the robots in the different inspection use cases.

2.3.1 Viaduct visual inspection

The use case of the viaduct visual inspection requires the creation of a previous 3D map using a total station. This map will be a point cloud that identifies a coordinate origin for the entire

inspection system. To create this map, operators must ensure that the ENU system is followed ($x = \text{east}$, $y = \text{north}$, $z = \text{up}$). This map can be reused in future inspections of the viaduct.

The drone that will be used for this use case is the AERO-CAM. This drone is built from a DJI Matrice 600 Pro on which the necessary components to operate have been installed. To be able to perform the GNSS-free localization and navigation, the drone is equipped with an Ouster lidar sensor, model OS0 with 128 channels. This sensor is located under the avionics with a small custom anti-vibration structure. As said, this lidar sensor is used to perform an in-flight location of the drone movements, but it is also used to locate the drone's reference system with respect to the global inspection reference system. To complement this lidar, the drone has a 9-axis IMU that works at 400hz. In addition, the system includes a laser altimeter that allows more precise landings. The processing of all the sensor readings is carried out on an onboard computer, model Intel NUC i7.

Figure 3. AERO-CAM.

The drone system has its own localization and navigation algorithm (T_{LD}) that has its origin in the take-off point (L). Since this location may vary, the complete system requires a second localization system that establishes the 3D transformation between the initial drone pose and the global reference system (T_{GL}), expressed in ENU coordinates at the origin of the map created by the total station (G). These transforms can be visualized in the following figure:

Figure 4. Full transformation system.

Therefore, the system has two localization processes that are described below:

1. Global localization system

The function of the global location system is to find the transform T_{GL} , which establishes the connection between the global reference system of the 3D map of the viaduct and the drone localization system. Finding this transform is crucial, as it will allow the drone to safely navigate to areas selected by the inspector as interesting to inspect without maintaining the same take-off position between flights. This is especially beneficial for eliminating the total station dependency beyond creating the initial 3D map. In addition, since the viaduct can be found in an inaccessible area, the take-off position may not be replicated between flights or even inspections on different days.

The transform T_{GL} is fixed and will only vary during the flight if another transform with better accuracy has been obtained. Therefore, this global localization system is designed to calculate the transform at the initial instant, just before the drone takes off. During the flight, this system could continue working by calculating the transform between the drone current position and the base map (T_{GD}), so that if the accuracy of the transform improves, update it. This last case can be visualized in the following figure:

Figure 5. In-air global localization transformation system.

This localization system does not have to be executed on the onboard computer, and it can be executed on a ground computer since it does not require the calculation to be instantaneous. In this case, the onboard computer would send the data to the ground computer, which will perform the calculations and send the result back to the drone.

To find the correspondence between the previous 3D map generated by the total station and the data from the onboard sensors, we are working on an algorithm that makes use of the geometric characteristics of the point clouds. Specifically, the algorithm makes use of the characteristics of both clouds extracting FPFH (*Fast Point Feature Histogram*) features. These features encode the geometric properties of the k nearest neighbors of a given point using the average curvature of the multidimensional histogram around that point. Among its advantages, these features are invariant in position and a certain level of noise. After this feature extraction process, the algorithm applies RANSAC (*Random Sample Consensus*) to find a first approximation between both inputs. The result is then corrected with the assumptions of the problem and ICP (*Iterative Closest Point*) is applied to refine the result. The following figure shows a block diagram of the main steps of the algorithm:

Figure 6. Point clouds matching diagram.

To improve this process, some assumptions can be made that simplify the problem and work in all possible scenarios:

- The map obtained with the total station is cleaned so that it only contains information about the viaduct. This prevents unwanted objects from appearing.
- The coordinate origin of the total station map is expressed in ENU. Also, this origin is aligned with the horizon, so it will have 0 degrees in pitch and roll.
- The take-off point of the drone is aligned with the horizon, so it will have 0 degrees in pitch and roll.
- The absolute yaw orientation of the drone is known thanks to the onboard magnetometer. Therefore, the approximate rotation matrix between the lidar and the total station map is known beforehand.
- The GPS position of the total station map origin is known approximately. If the drone has GPS coverage at the take-off point, its approximate position can be obtained. Thus, an initial guess would be obtained for the position.

Of course, there are other possible solutions for this problem, such as applying Deep Learning to find the correspondence or others such as a statistical filter (for example, particle filter) in

which the similarity of both maps with the displacement is evaluated. The development of this algorithm is still under evaluation and can be modified.

2. Relative localization system

The function of the relative localization system is to find the transform T_{LD} , which describes the motion of the drone from its take-off point. This take-off point will be a flat area near the viaduct and is assumed to be flat with respect to the horizon so that the drone can take off safely. This localization is performed only with the onboard sensors and does not require any data beforehand, only the current sensor reading. Of course, it is desirable that this localization is as accurate as possible and, above all, minimize drifts in time as much as possible to avoid a significant divergence between reality and the pose in which the drone thinks it is.

Figure 7. Relative localization transformation system.

The relative localization system makes use of the lidar and the 9-axis IMU to calculate the drone's pose at each instant. The algorithm operates at high frequency in real time, updating the pose at the same frequency as the IMU, which in the case of AERO-CAM is 400Hz. This algorithm is executed entirely onboard the drone in the Intel NUC equipped. Despite running in real time, this algorithm has the highest processing load among the programs executed by the drone.

The relative localization system is of vital importance to the system, as it is used to provide localization feedback to the drone control algorithm so it can ensure a stable flight by navigating autonomously to the desired target points.

The localization algorithm is based on LIO-SAM [3], where the following general architecture, adapted to AERO-CAM, is proposed:

Figure 8. LIDAR+IMU localization general architecture.

This architecture establishes a tightly coupled fusion between the lidar and the IMU, builds a factor graph in which the measurements made by the sensors are integrated to build and optimize the map. The IMU pre-integration is based on [4]. An important clarification is that to integrate the IMU measurements, the magnetometer is not used, only the angular velocities and linear accelerations. Since the double integration of an IMU leads to large drift, the architecture proposes the short-term integration of the IMU, correcting its bias thanks to the localization at lower frequency in the built map using the information of the lidar point cloud. In order to process everything in real time, the algorithm discards lidar readings if they are not sufficiently displaced with respect to the previous reading considered (lidar keyframes). In this way, a lot of redundant information that would increase the computational load is discarded. Between lidar keyframes, the IMU readings are integrated, converging in a node of the graph that would be the state of the location at that given instant. The following diagram, simplified from [3], shows a schematic of the processing of the sensor readings:

Figure 9. Localization factor graph example.

As already mentioned, the result of all this processing is the location of the drone without GPS with a high frequency (400Hz) that serves the control algorithm to proceed with the AERO-CAM.

2.3.2 Refinery pipes inspection

As with the viaduct visual inspection, the refinery pipes inspection use case requires the creation of a previous 3D map. Given the nature of a refinery, where the maze of pipes and structures would make it difficult to create an accurate 3D map by the total station, the alternative solution is to use the HYBRID platform equipped with a 3D lidar to perform a flight to create an accurate point cloud. Since these flights will be outdoors, the point cloud will be correctly georeferenced, so that, when selecting a 3D point (x, y, z), it can be related to its GPS coordinate. Again, to create this map, operators must ensure that the ENU system is followed (x = east, y = north, z = up). Also, this map can be reused in future refinery pipes inspections.

The HYBRID platform is a customized drone equipped with the necessary sensors for operation. Specifically, for autonomous navigation, the drone has an autopilot with a built-in GPS receiver, 9-axis IMU and barometric altimeter. Again, to be able to perform the GNSS-free localization and navigation, and possible obstacle detection, the drone is equipped with an Ouster lidar sensor, model OS0 with 128 channels. Given the very limited space available on this platform and the need to see the area just below and above it to land on the pipe and detect obstacles, the lidar is mounted horizontally, but part of its field of view is blocked by the drone's frame. In addition, the 90° vertical field of view is not sufficient. To overcome this problem, the platform has two mirrors that deflect the lidar lasers upwards and downwards, thus being able to observe all the areas of interest. Figure 10 illustrates this concept. The processing of all the sensor readings is carried out on an onboard computer, model Intel NUC i7.

Figure 10. HYBRID Lidar mirror concept.

Like the viaduct visual inspection use case, this platform has two localization systems which are explained below:

1. Global localization system

The function of the global positioning system is to guide the platform from its take-off point to an area near the pipe that the inspector has selected to inspect. The pipe selected by the inspector is chosen thanks to the previously created 3D map of the area. Since this map is georeferenced, the GPS coordinate of the area of the pipe to be inspected can be obtained.

Therefore, this global localization system does not involve too much complexity since, regardless the drone's take-off point, the algorithm guides it to an area close to the pipe if the GPS signal is good. As soon as this GPS signal starts to degrade and obstacles start to appear around, the navigation system starts to make use of the relative localization system explained in the following section.

The following figure shows a scheme of the global localization reference systems, where the transformation T_{GD} is direct since GPS is used for the take-off point and G .

Figure 11. HYBRID Global Localization system.

2. Relative localization system

The function of the relative localization system is to find the transform T_{LD} , which describes the motion of the drone from the point where the GPS navigation ends until the landing position on the pipe. This point from where the relative navigation starts is referred to in the figures as L . Like the AERO-CAM, this localization is performed only with onboard sensors and does not require any data beforehand, only the current sensor reading.

Figure 12. Pipe landing transformation system.

This relative localization algorithm is the same as the one used in AERO-CAM, with the only difference being that in the HYBRID platform the lidar has a smaller field of view. In the use case of the refinery pipes inspection, this situation is compensated since the relative localization is done in dense areas of elements, so the algorithm receives enough information to work correctly.

For the final approximation, the onboard computer of the HYBRID platform is running a pipe detection algorithm chosen by the inspector, which compares the point cloud received by the lidar at that moment with the preloaded 3D map. This algorithm has as output the transform T_{DP} , which, seen from the drone's point of view, is the relative movements that it must perform to land on the pipe.

In this way, by executing the relative localization algorithm and the pipe detection algorithm, the control can perform relative navigation until it finally lands.

2.3.3 Refinery tank inspection

The use case of the refinery tank inspection requires the AEROX flight platform, which performs a contact inspection thanks to the robotic arm installed on it. In order to fully complete the inspection, AEROX must navigate from its take-off point to the contact zone in the tank where the inspection is to be performed. Once there, the end effector will contact the tank and the platform will run its control algorithm getting feedback from the robotic arm sensors. The AEROX platform is equipped with an autopilot with a GPS receiver for global positioning, a 9-axis IMU and a barometric altimeter. In addition, the drone has at its disposal Intel RealSense T265 cameras that run an internal localization algorithm and send to AEROX a relative position and orientation from the point where they were started. These cameras work with the stereo technology of their fish-eye type lenses and are used to perform relative localization of the drone.

Figure 13: Intel RealSense T265.

The flight of the AEROX can be divided into two phases:

1. Approach

The approach phase from the take-off point to the contact with the tank is assisted by the sensors and the pilot. During this phase, a sensor fusion algorithm is executed that considers the GPS positioning and relative localization of the Intel RealSense T265 cameras. This will make the navigation to the tank contact assisted for the pilot, being able to execute the maneuver smoothly.

2. Contact inspection

In the contact phase, the GPS signal will be degraded due to high interference from metallic structures in the environment. That is why in this case the relative location information of the drone is given only by the Intel RealSense T265 cameras. This relative location is only for

information purposes for the inspection since the control during the contact phase is carried out by the sensors installed in it, as previously mentioned.

Figure 14. Refinery Tank AEROX Inspection transform system.

2.3.4 Viaduct bearings inspection and sensor and target installation

Differing from the viaduct visual inspection, all other applications for viaducts have one thing in common, the aerial robot interacts physically with the viaduct structure, sometimes needing to get close to narrow spaces like the one between the top of the pillar and the deck. Thus, the aerial platform should be small enough to access the narrow spaces but powerful enough to carry the necessary tools to interact with the viaduct structure. The platform selected for these use cases is VIAD-DRONE, a specialized aerial platform designed to adapt to different inspection applications for viaducts. This platform has a modular design, in which the same base platform can be adapted with some accessories or add-ons to fulfil the specific needs of each use case. More details about the platform and its adaptations can be found in deliverable D4.1.

The selected platform is small and prepared for contact with the viaduct structure, so it has a limited payload capacity. Therefore, in this case, the number, size and weight of the navigation sensors should be as low as possible. The proposed solution is to use two cameras for relative localization via visual-inertial odometry (VIO) and one 2D lidar for global localization in the viaduct. In the following, the solution will be detailed.

1. Relative localization

The objective of the relative localization is to give a fast estimation of the robot pose relative to the take-off point. Like in the previous use case, this take-off point will be a flat area free of obstacles near the viaduct. This localization is unaware of the viaduct, and it is performed only with onboard sensors and without any prior information of the environment. This relative localization is the base of the localization system, allowing the robot to perform a stable flight

and being able to return to the take-off position if needed. However, this estimation might drift over time.

The proposed solution for the relative localization in this use case is to perform visual-inertial odometry (VIO) with one or two cameras pointing at different positions. The first approach is to have one camera pointing forward and the other one looking down and back. The work on integration and experimentation phases will determine the final configuration of the cameras. Apart from the visual data gathered by the cameras, this algorithm will also integrate high-rate data from an IMU.

Visual-inertial odometry is the process of estimating the state of the sensor suite using the camera and IMU measurements. Cameras and IMUs are complementary sensor types. A camera accumulates the photons during the exposure time to get a 2D image. Therefore, they are precise during slow motion and provide rich information, which is useful for other perception tasks, such as place recognition. However, they have a limited output rate ($\sim 30\text{-}50\text{Hz}$), suffer from scale ambiguity in a monocular setup, and are not robust to scenes characterized by low texture, high speed motions (due to motion blur) and High Dynamic Range (HDR) (which may cause over- or under-exposure of the image). By contrast, an IMU is a proprioceptive sensor measuring the angular velocity and the external acceleration acting upon it. An IMU is scene-independent, which renders it unaffected by the aforementioned difficulties for cameras. Thus, it is the ideal complement to cameras to achieve robustness in low texture, high speed, and HDR scenarios. Additionally, an IMU has a high output rate ($\sim 400\text{-}1,000\text{Hz}$). However, it suffers from poor signal-noise ratio at low accelerations and low angular velocities. Due to the presence of sensor biases, the motion estimated from an IMU alone tends to accumulate drift quickly. Therefore, a combination of both cameras and IMUs can provide accurate and robust state estimation in different situations.

The algorithm to be used in the final implementation will depend on the selection of the camera. For instance, some cameras like the Intel RealSense T265 integrates visual-inertial odometry without the need for extra processing. However, preliminary experiments in a viaduct showed that this sensor is not the best choice for this kind of scenario. The problem is that the small baseline makes it useful when there are objects closer than 10 meters, not farther. The idea then is to use a stereo camera with a bigger baseline or to use couples of monocular cameras creating a customized stereo pair. Then, we can run algorithms like VINS-MONO [5] or SVO [6].

2. Global localization

The global localization covers the need for the robot to know, with a certain level of accuracy, its position and orientation relative to the viaduct structure. This is necessary to perform the desired application, e.g., visually inspecting the bearings, installing a sensor box on top of the pillar, or installing a target on the viaduct structure.

Of course, this global localization uses the same reference system than the viaduct visual inspection described in the previous section. This is critical, as the targets should be installed in positions determined by the visual inspection.

As mentioned before, the limits in size, weight and processing power of this robot affect the sensors that it can carry. Therefore, the proposal for the global localization is to use a small 2D lidar with a mirror, so it can measure the distance to the pillar in front of the robot and, at the same time, to the deck above it. Figure 15 shows a scheme of this localization approach. The lidar measurements are in red, while the cameras field of view are in green. This scheme also highlights the different reference frames, the global $\{G\}$, attached to the viaduct, and the local $\{L\}$, on the take-off location.

Figure 15: Scheme of the localization system for VIAD-DRONE.

The first approach is to detect the pillar and the deck using RANSAC (*Random Sample Consensus*). Considering the global reference frame with the same orientation as the viaduct and knowing the geometry of the viaduct section, we can directly estimate the x axis with the distance to the pillar, the z axis with the distance to the deck and the y axis and the yaw with the relative position to both the pillar and the deck.

To be more accurate and given the fact that a map (point cloud) of the viaduct is available, the idea is to apply ICP (*Iterative Closest Point*) to find the correspondence between the lidar measurements and the map. This way, a single lidar measurement can estimate the pose of the robot in the global reference frame.

The proposed solution also considers the use of a robotic total station to contribute to the global localization. Using this kind of sensor has a great advantage as it can give the most accurate position measurements, plus it gives these measurements directly in the global reference frame. However, it also has some drawbacks like the low rate of the measurements (less than 10Hz), the dependency on the communication channel to send the measurements to the robot and the need of being in the line of sight. Moreover, this is an expensive sensor that could be carried every time to perform regular inspections.

Figure 16 shows the scheme of the localization system in the viaduct using the total station for global localization. To let the total station follow the robot and measure its position, the robot needs to carry a small reflective prism, which should always be in the line of sight of the total station.

Figure 16: Scheme of the localization system for VIAD-DRONE using a total station for global localization.

Of course, the proposed localization system allows the use of all the available sensors, so the total station is not only an alternative for the global localization but a complement that can be used together with the 2D lidar. In fact, this combination would increase the overall reliability of the system, allowing the robot to fly out of the line of sight of the total station and still getting a global localization input.

Figure 17 shows the architecture of the localization system for the viaduct use cases. On one side, both cameras and the IMU are used to obtain a fast relative estimation from a visual-inertial odometry algorithm. On the other side, at a lower rate (around 10 Hz), the 2D lidar measurements are pre-processed to obtain the global localization estimation. Finally, both relative and global estimations are fused in a Recursive Bayesian Filter (RBF), which gives the final high-rate global localization estimation to be used by the robot.

Figure 17: Architecture of the viaduct localization system.

2.3.5 Tunnel local inspection

The tunnel inspection will be performed by a robotic system that integrates a ground robot or UGV (Unmanned Ground Vehicle) and an aerial robot or UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle), as represented in Figure 18. The general inspection of the tunnel will be performed by the UGV, while the local inspection (closer view in the inspection points) will be carried out by the aerial robot. This aerial robot is known as the TTDRONE (Tunnel Tethered DRONE), as it is connected to the ground robot with a tethered system through which the power supply and data transmission between vehicles are carried out. More information about both robots can be found in project deliverable D4.1.

Figure 18: Tunnel inspection robotic system integrates a UGV and an aerial robot.

In brief, in the local inspection task, the UGV will stop in some Point of Interest (POI) where potential defects have been detected. At this point, the aerial robot will take off autonomously from the ground robot and will navigate close to detected defects to carry out the inspection with more details. When the detailed inspection task is reached, the aerial robot will land on the ground robot again. To enable this behavior, fast and accurate pose estimation is necessary.

The developed system is designed to obtain pose estimations (3D position and orientation) of the aerial robot w.r.t. the UGV. The UGV has its own localization system, described in deliverable D5.2, which estimates its global pose in the tunnel reference frame. Combining both location estimates enables to obtain the aerial robot global localization. Hence, the objective is to calculate the aerial robot pose relative to the UGV in order to enable the aerial robot to perform its tunnel local inspection mission.

The proposed aerial robot localization method adopts an approach based on tracking active visual markers attached to the UGV. Small lights will be deployed at known positions and configurations on the surface of the UGV. Using dedicated cameras and suitable image processing techniques, the aerial robot will detect them and will use their coordinates on the image plane as input of a Recursive Bayesian Filter (RBF) that will estimate with suitable accuracy the pose of the aerial robot w.r.t. the ground robot.

System description

The main components of the designed visual marker-based localization system are two cameras, the visual markers and a processing core. Figure 19 shows a scheme of the proposed localization system. The aerial robot is equipped with two visual cameras that allow the aerial robot to localize itself inside the tunnel. One camera points towards the back/down direction of the robot. It is used to detect and track the visual markers attached to the UGV. The second camera points towards the frontal direction. It is used to estimate the aerial robot odometry using the visual features in the environment. Moreover, the visual markers on the UGV are active LED markers.

Figure 19: Scheme of the distribution of the cameras and the LEDs markers of the tunnel localization system.

The **rear camera** is taken as the main sensor of the localization method. Table 2 presents some cameras suitable for recognizing and tracking the LED markers described below. Depending on the size, lumens and illumination frequency of the selected LEDs, the cameras should have some specifications to be able to perform the recognition and tracking task. All cameras are RGB sensors with high resolution and frame rate, configurable exposure time, wide field of view, and have a low size and weight.

Table 2: Cameras for recognizing and tracking the LED markers of the localization system.

Sensor	Resolution	Frame Rate [fps]	Configurable Exposure Time	FOV [deg]	Size [mm]	Weight [g]
OpenMV H7 Plus	1920 x 1080	30	Yes	70.8 x 55.6	45 x 36 x 29	17
Intel Real Sense D435i	1920 x 1080	30	Yes	69 x 42	90 x 25 x 25	75
DUO MLX	752 x 480	45	Yes	70 x 165	52 x 25 x 13	12,5

The **frontal camera** is used for performing visual odometry tasks. The aim is to have an accurate pose estimation even when no LED markers are detected due to occlusions or even when the UGV is not in the aerial robot's field of view. The frontal camera is an Intel RealSense Tracking Camera T265 which provides a low drift robot pose combining grayscale fisheye lenses cameras and IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) measurements. This sensor can capture 163° wide-angle images at 100 FPS in indoor and outdoor environments at light levels as low as 15 lux. Some visual odometry results in a preliminary tunnel scenario will be shown in the following.

The **visual markers** are composed of at least three LEDs sensors. These markers are suitable for the tunnel use case due to no additional lighting of the scene is necessary for tracking the UGV. The devices used for that purpose are shown in Figure 20-Left. They are cool white SMD (Surface Mounted Device) sensors of 3W power, 160-240 lm of luminous intensity and 125° of viewing angle. Figure 20-Right shows the LED Driver used as a constant current controller. Each LED marker is powered with 12 V batteries.

Figure 20: Left) iPixel 3W LED. Right) FemtoBuck Constant Current LED Driver.

The visual markers will be deployed at known positions and configurations on the surface of the ground robot. Figure 21 shows the designed 3D printed blobs that enclose the LED sensors. These blobs allow the LED sensors to be detected as bright spots instead of as sparse colored light rays on the image plane of the rear camera, which enhances the accuracy of the pose estimations in poor lighting environments. Moreover, these 3D printed blobs simplify the marker finding and correspondence finding tasks as they can be matched using their colors, as well as their known position and configuration on the surface of the UGV.

Figure 21: Left) CAD model of the designed blobs. Right) yellow, white and red 3D printed blobs that enclose the LED sensors.

The **processing core** of the proposed localization system must have high computational burden to accomplish the above-mentioned requirements (low latency, online computation, etc.). The proposed processing core for the designed localization system is the Intel NUC i7. On the other hand, NVIDIA Jetson TX2 could be another candidate for the processing unit if GPU

computing were necessary. Despite these two processing devices for the localization system, there are currently many other candidates on the live market.

Sensors such as IMUs are also integrated into the proposed localization method. The IMU of the autopilot of the aerial robot is used to enhance the 3D orientation estimations of the proposed Recursive Bayesian Filter. The integration of the above measurements is consistent with the tunnel use case operation, features of the environment and the permitted payload of the aerial platform described in the deliverable D4.1.

It is important to recall that the TTDRONE will have a third camera that will perform the inspection tasks (i.e., taking images on the inspection points for detecting possible defects). This camera will be placed on the upper part of the vehicle, held by a gimbal. It is a commercial photography camera; hence, it cannot be used for localization tasks.

Localization method

The proposed localization method aims to obtain a robust and accurate aerial robot pose estimation relative to the UGV in order to enable the aerial robot to autonomously perform local inspection tasks in GNSS-denied environments. The proposed method is based on an RBF (Recursive Bayesian Filter). The adopted scheme is depicted in Figure 22. The method is composed of 4 main stages: sensor measurements pre-processing stage, RBF prediction stage, RBF update stage, and transform to global stage. The filter fuses measurements gathered by the rear camera, the frontal camera and the IMU of the autopilot of the aerial robot.

Figure 22: Software architecture of the tunnel localization method for the aerial robot.

The **sensor measurements pre-processing stage** receives as input the images from the rear camera. These images are processed to carry out the LED markers detection and tracking tasks. The coordinates of the detected LED markers on the plane image are used as input to the update stage of the filter.

The **RBF prediction stage** receives as input the IMU measurements and the pose estimated by the visual odometry method. The visual odometry is computed matching the features obtained

in consecutive frontal camera images. The pose estimations from the visual odometry method are statistically fused with the IMU measurements to predict the current pose of the aerial robot.

The **RBF update stage** receives as inputs the predicted localization of the aerial robot and the coordinates of the detected LED markers on the plane image of the rear camera. The output of this stage is the pose estimations of the aerial robot inside the tunnel w.r.t the UGV.

The **transform to global** stage receives the RBF estimation relative to the UGV and, knowing the latter's pose in the tunnel reference frame, transforms the estimation to this reference frame to finally estimate the global localization of the aerial robot in the tunnel.

The integration of the above measurements is consistent with the tunnel local inspection task and features of the environment. When no LED markers are detected due to occlusions or when the UGV is not in the aerial robot's field of view, the localization method will be able to estimate the aerial robot pose integrating only the pose estimations from the visual odometry method and the IMU measurements. The resulting pose estimation is not expected to be very accurate, but it will be enough for navigation in spaces with distant obstacles. When the aerial robot is detecting and tracking the LED markers deployed on the surface of the UGV, the localization method will integrate measurements from the frontal camera, the IMU and the rear camera. The pose estimation will be more accurate, which is consistent with the fact that the robot will have to navigate in challenging scenarios.

Figure 23 shows some results that were obtained in a preliminary experiment that was carried out in a tunnel with similar features to the PILOTING tunnel use case scenario described in deliverable 3.2. The frontal camera presented above, Intel RealSense Tracking Camera T265, was used to perceive the environment and for estimating the aerial robot localization performing visual odometry methods. Results of the designed localization system will be shown in the following deliverable D5.3 ("Final version of advanced autonomous functionalities for aerial robots"). All software stages have been implemented to run in ROS (Robot Operating System) Melodic under Ubuntu 18.04.

Figure 23: Pose of the aerial robot estimated with visual odometry methods in a preliminary tunnel experiment.

3. Aerial interaction control

This section presents the general control architecture used in the PILOTING aerial robots for achieving stability and control of their operation. As has been described in D4.1, in PILOTING five main aerial robots are being developed for the different use cases: AERO-CAM, HYBRID, TTDRONE, VIAD-DRONE and AEROX. Each aerial robot will operate in different environmental conditions, some of them flying very close to surfaces and objects in the environment and with physical interaction. A modular control architecture has been adopted in PILOTING to develop the flight controllers of the platforms, that can be adapted to the specific flight conditions of each one.

The next subsection presents the generic dynamic model of an aerial robot with manipulator arms interacting with the environment, including the different phenomena that affect the dynamics. Then, a generic modular control architecture is formulated for this general dynamic model, which includes attitude and position controllers.

The main differences for the control of the PILOTING aerial robots will be in the attitude controllers, which account for the different forces and torques that appear during their operation. The position controller can be formulated jointly for all the platforms once the robot has been stabilized in attitude compensating the external forces and torques. The following subsections will detail the specific conditions of the operation of each aerial platform, the generated forces and torques and the form of the adapted attitude controller for each platform.

3.1 Modular controller architecture

This subsection presents the general dynamic model of a multirotor with a manipulator arm including the aerodynamic propulsive model of the actuators. Then, the modular architecture of the multirotor controller which includes the attitude and position controllers is formulated.

3.1.1 Multirotor dynamic model

The full dynamic model of a multirotor with a manipulator arm is very complex since it includes the coupled dynamics of the quadrotor aerial vehicle and the manipulator [7]. The dynamic model for a multirotor and a k -link manipulator arm can be obtained using the Euler-Lagrange formulation [8]. The generalized coordinates of the multirotor with manipulator system can be defined as $\xi = [p \ \eta \ \gamma]^T \in \mathbb{R}^n$, with $n = 6 + k$; where $p = [x \ y \ z]^T$ represents the translation coordinates of the multirotor center of gravity relative to the inertial frame, $\eta = [\phi \ \theta \ \psi]^T$ describes the vehicle attitude by the classical roll, pitch, yaw Euler angles commonly used in aerospace applications, and $\gamma = [\gamma_1 \ \gamma_2 \ \dots \ \gamma_k]^T$ are the joint angles of the arm. The dynamics of each coordinate can be described by the general Euler-Lagrange equations as

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{\xi}_i} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial \xi_i} = F + F_{ext} + F_{cont} \quad (1)$$

where F is the vector of forces and torques generated by the actuators. It can be decomposed into the thrust forces F_Q and moments, τ_Q generated by the rotors, and the torque of each link of the manipulator, τ_M . External forces and moments are represented by F_{ext} , which include wind and other atmospheric perturbations, and F_{cont} , which include the contact forces and moments of the end effector with the structure surfaces that it is inspecting. The Euler-Lagrange equations are derived directly from the energy expressed in the generalized coordinates. First, the system Lagrangian is derived as the difference between the kinetic and the potential energies of the system. For the typical manipulators, the Lagrangian function is

$$L(\xi, \dot{\xi}) = K(\xi, \dot{\xi}) - P(\xi) \quad (2)$$

where K represents the kinetic energy and P is the potential energy. Thus, after some computations, the equations of motion can be obtained as:

$$M(\xi)\ddot{\xi} + C(\xi, \dot{\xi})\dot{\xi} + G(\xi) = F_{prop}(\xi) + F_{ext} + F_{cont} \quad (3)$$

Here, M is the inertia matrix, the Coriolis and centrifugal terms are represented by C and the gravitational force terms are described by G . Vector $F_{prop}(\xi)$ encompasses actuator forces and torques exerted by the propellers. These forces and torques depend on the state of the multirotor due to the aerodynamic effects that arise working close to the bridge and the servo actuators of the arm joints.

3.1.2 Thrust model with aerodynamic effects

When a rotary-wing UAV has to fly close to a surface, as pipes, tunnel walls, bridge deck or piers, the airflow entering the rotor and coming out of it may interfere with these surfaces, changing the thrust and torque characteristics of the rotors [9]. These aerodynamic effects may be significant in several of the application tasks of the different PILOTING aerial robots.

The thrust generated by each rotor and the reaction torque due to rotor drag are generally accepted to be proportional to the square of the angular velocity of the rotor, Ω , when flying on free air:

$$T_n = C_T \Omega^2 \quad (4)$$

$$Q_n = C_D \Omega^2 \quad (5)$$

The thrust and drag coefficients C_T and C_D can be determined by static thrust tests. However, when the multirotor is flying close to the ground, the ceiling or other surfaces, the rotor thrust and drag model are no longer valid, due to the aerodynamic effects. To account for these effects, the thrust model is modified as:

$$T = T_n + T_a(\xi) \quad (6)$$

Where $T_a(\xi)$ is the additional thrust due to aerodynamic effects, which depends on the relative position of the rotors with respect to the surfaces in the environment.

3.1.3 Aerial robot controller

In the last years, there have been some attempts to derive general methodologies for controlling aerial vehicles equipped with robotic manipulators [10] [11]. Control and stabilization of an aerial system composed of an aerial vehicle and a manipulator arm are complex due to the variable dynamics of the vehicle when the arm is moving, grasping, and manipulating objects. This effect is due to the modification of the aerial vehicle mass centre and mass distribution when performing these operations. Similarly, the contact forces that appear when interacting with the environment are an additional influence on the dynamics. These effects are usually not considered explicitly in the vehicle controllers and hence left to the integral action in the feedback loop. In this respect, [12] presents stability limits within which the changing mass-inertia parameters of the system would not destabilize quadrotors and helicopters with standard PID controllers. Controllers based on integral backstepping which considers the mass variation produced when the arm is moving have also been implemented in quadrotors with multi-link manipulators [13] [14]. The dynamics of aerial vehicles in contact with the environment have also been analysed [15].

As mentioned above, backstepping has shown as an effective control technique for aerial platforms [13] [14], and will be used in the project as a baseline controller for the different aerial robots. Here we consider standard coplanar multirotors, which are underactuated systems with four control inputs:

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} U_z \\ U_\phi \\ U_\theta \\ U_\psi \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} T \\ \tau_\phi \\ \tau_\theta \\ \tau_\psi \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

and six degrees of freedom (DoF). The states, z and η (the three system attitude angles) have been chosen as the controlled variables, and then the $[x, y]$ position control loops are built on top of the attitude control loops, generating desired attitude references that are passed to the inner loops.

3.1.3.1 Attitude Control

The attitude controller is implemented in an inner loop and its proper operation is crucial for the system since it will be in charge of stabilizing the vehicle as well as maintaining the desired orientation. Defining attitude input control vector as $U_\eta = [U_\phi \ U_\theta \ U_\psi]^T$ and following the developments presented in [8], the attitude controller can be written as:

$$U_\eta = M_\eta [K_1 e_\eta + K_2 \dot{e}_\eta + K_3 \chi_\eta + \dot{\eta}_d] + C_\eta + G_\eta - \tilde{M}_{\eta\gamma} \ddot{\gamma} - \tilde{M}_\eta \ddot{\eta} - \tilde{\tau}_c \quad (8)$$

Here, the tracking error, e_η , the angular velocity tracking error, $e_{\dot{\eta}}$ and the integral of the angular position tracking error, χ_η are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} e_\eta &= \eta_d - \eta \in \mathbb{R}^3 \\ \chi_\eta &= \int_0^t e_\eta(t) dt \in \mathbb{R}^3 \\ e_{\dot{\eta}} &= k_\eta e_\eta + \lambda_\eta \chi_\eta + \dot{\eta}_d - \dot{\eta} \in \mathbb{R}^3 \\ K_1 &= \mathbb{I}_3 - \lambda_\eta^2 + k_\eta \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3} \\ K_2 &= k_\eta + k_{\dot{\eta}} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3} \\ K_3 &= -k_\eta \lambda_\eta \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3} \end{aligned}$$

where k_η , $k_{\dot{\eta}}$ and λ_η are positive diagonal controller matrix gain. The matrix $C_\eta \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and is the lower part of the Coriolis and centrifugal forces vector. The terms $\tilde{M}_\eta \ddot{\eta}$ and $\tilde{M}_{\eta\gamma} \dot{\gamma}$ introduce the estimation of the dynamic coupling and $\tilde{\tau}_c$ the estimation of the torque induced by the contact force, F_E .

3.1.3.2 Position Control

The position controller generates the desired attitude corresponding to the position references given by the system. Now, if U_x and U_y are defined as the virtual position control inputs for the XY position controller, the position controller can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} U_z &= \frac{m}{\cos \phi \sin \theta} [g + K_z e_z + K_{\dot{z}} e_{\dot{z}} + L_z \chi_z + \ddot{z}_d] - \tilde{F}_{E_z} \\ U_x &= \frac{m}{U_z} [K_x e_x + K_{\dot{x}} e_{\dot{x}} + L_x \chi_x + \ddot{x}_d] - \tilde{F}_{E_x} \\ U_y &= -\frac{m}{U_z} [K_y e_y + K_{\dot{y}} e_{\dot{y}} + L_y \chi_y + \ddot{y}_d] - \tilde{F}_{E_y} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} K_p &= 1 - \lambda_p^2 + k_p, \quad p = x, y, z \\ K_{\dot{p}} &= k_p + k_{\dot{p}}, \quad p = x, y, z \\ L_p &= -k_p \lambda_p, \quad p = x, y, z \end{aligned}$$

where k_p , $k_{\dot{p}}$ and λ_p with $p = x, y, z$ are positive constant controller gains, and e_x , e_y and e_z are the position tracking error for the generalized position coordinates. The speed tracking errors are defined as $e_{\dot{x}}$, $e_{\dot{y}}$ and $e_{\dot{z}}$ and the integral of the angular position tracking error are defined by χ_z , χ_x and χ_y . The components of the generalized force vector, $\tilde{F}_E = [\tilde{F}_{E_x} \quad \tilde{F}_{E_y} \quad \tilde{F}_{E_z}]^T$ have been used to describe multirotor dynamics effects due to the interaction between the system and the environment.

In the following subsections, the dynamic model used for control and the attitude controller will be presented for each aerial platform.

3.2 AERO-CAM

The AERO-CAM is the aerial robot used for the visual inspection of the viaduct. It is based on a hexacopter multirotor aerial platform, with the inspection camera mounted on the upper part of the aerial vehicle.

From the control point of view, it is a standard multirotor without physical interaction, and the simplified dynamic model used by several autopilots can be considered in this case. This simplified model supposes that the aerial robot will not have fast movements and the roll and pitch angles will be small. From this, the attitude dynamic equations get decoupled and standard linear controllers in cascaded architecture can be used for attitude control. The only significant external forces and torques are caused by the wind F_{ext} , which will be treated as perturbations and compensated by the controller.

The simplified dynamic model of the AERO-CAM aerial robot for controller derivation can be expressed as:

$$M\ddot{\xi} + C(\xi, \dot{\xi})\dot{\xi} + G = F_{prop} + F_{ext} \quad (10)$$

And the general expression of the attitude controller will result in:

$$U_{\eta} = [K_1 e_{\eta} + K_2 \dot{e}_{\eta} + K_3 \chi_{\eta}] \quad (11)$$

3.3 HYBRID

The HYBRID is a specialized robot for inspecting magnetic pipes in the refinery pipe inspection use case. It is composed of two different platforms: the aerial platform, and the satellite, which will be in charge of the UT inspection. The Satellite robot is gathered in the aerial platform, and it is deployed over the pipe once the HYBRID has landed on the pipe, and is attached to it.

The main function of the HYBRID aerial platform is to fly and navigate in the refinery to the area of interest and land on a pipe that needs inspection. It will have to fly in the refinery outdoor environment where prevalent winds can be significant, and modified by the surrounding pipes and devices, generating external forces to the multirotor F_{ext} varying with the position of the robot and time.

Landing and take-off from the pipe are the most critical phases for the HYBRID aerial robot control. The contact forces in the landing include the magnetic forces from the magnetic devices and the contact forces generated by the platform inertia when landing. Both need to be considered in the model F_{land} , and in the controller.

Furthermore, in the final phases of the landing, the aerodynamic interference of the airflow from the rotors with the pipe where it is landing and the adjacent pipes gains more importance, as shown in Figure 24 with preliminary CFD simulations. This will make that the forces and torques generated by the propellers vary with the relative position of the aerial robot with respect to the pipes when landing, $F_{prop}(\xi)$.

Figure 24. Airflow of a multirotor flying over several pipes (CFD simulation).

With all these considerations, the dynamic model of the HYBRID aerial robot for controller derivation would result in:

$$M\ddot{\xi} + C(\xi, \dot{\xi})\dot{\xi} + G = F_{prop}(\xi) + F_{ext} + F_{land} \quad (12)$$

And the general expression of the attitude controller for the VIAD-DRONE will result in:

$$U_{\eta} = M_{\eta}[K_1 e_{\eta} + K_2 \dot{e}_{\eta} + K_3 \chi_{\eta} + \ddot{\eta}_d] + C_{\eta} - \tilde{\tau}_{land} \quad (13)$$

3.4 TTDRONE

The main function of the TTDRONE is performing local inspections of the tunnel inner surfaces. The TTDRONE takes off from the CART robot and it is linked through a tether cable to a landing platform on the roof of the CART. This tether provides continuous power and communications to the TTDRONE multirotor, and it applies force to the cable to ensure it is stretched. This force F_{cable} has a module that varies depending on the cable extension and relative position, and its orientation angles vary depending also on the relative position of the TTDRONE and the CART robot.

Regarding the environmental conditions, the multirotor flies inside the tunnel close to the CART robot and other obstacles. Winds in the longitudinal direction of the tunnel can be present due to pressure differences between different sections, applying external forces to the multirotor F_{ext} . Furthermore, the aerial robot has to fly very close to the tunnel surfaces, where local aerodynamic effects coming from the interference of the airflow from the rotors appear, as shown in Figure 25 with preliminary CFD simulations. This will entail that the forces and

torques generated by the propellers vary with the relative position of the TTDRONE with respect to the tunnel inner walls and the CART, $F_{prop}(\xi)$.

Figure 25. CFD simulation of a multirotor flying inside a tunnel.

Then, the dynamic model of the TTDRONE for controller derivation would be the following:

$$M\ddot{\xi} + C(\xi, \dot{\xi})\dot{\xi} + G = F_{prop}(\xi) + F_{ext} + F_{cable} \quad (14)$$

And the general expression of the attitude controller for the TTDRONE will result in:

$$U_{\eta} = M_{\eta}[K_1 e_{\eta} + K_2 \dot{e}_{\eta} + K_3 \chi_{\eta} + \ddot{\eta}_d] + C_{\eta} - \tilde{\tau}_{cable} \quad (15)$$

3.5 VIAD-DRONE

The VIAD-DRONE is a specialized aerial platform designed to adapt to different inspection applications for viaducts. The main applications for this platform are bearings inspection, sensor box installation and target installation. In all these applications, the aerial robot must fly in close proximity and interact physically with the viaduct structure, sometimes needing to access narrow spaces like the one between the top of the pillar and the deck.

One of the functions of the VIAD-DRONE is the installation of sensors at the top of the pillars, and for that it has to carry the sensor and deploy it on the specific location on the upper part of the viaduct pillars, using the special device described in D4.1. The release of the sensor box will cause a change of mass and inertia characteristics in the different flight phases, and then the mass matrix $M(\xi)$ will vary.

The, VIAD-DRONE has to contact the pillar with a special device and apply a constant force during a given amount of time to fix the target firmly to the pillar. Furthermore, for inspection of the bearings and it has to fly and attach to the underside of the viaduct deck and beams. Whenever an aerial manipulator is touching or applying forces on the surfaces of the viaduct,

the contact forces have a significant role in the stability and control of the aerial platform. These forces are modelled as F_{cont} in the dynamic model of the robot.

Since it has to fly very close to the underside surfaces of the viaduct, the aerodynamic ceiling effect can be significant, modifying the thrust response of the rotors. When flying in confined spaces close to the bearings, other aerodynamic effects also arise. These effects are illustrated in Figure 26 with CFD preliminary simulations, and make that the forces and torques generated by the propellers vary with the relative position of the aerial robot with respect to the viaduct surfaces, $F_{prop}(\xi)$.

Figure 26. Aerodynamic effects of rotors flying close to the viaduct surfaces (preliminary CFD simulations).

Furthermore, wind can be significant in many cases when inspecting viaducts and will generate external forces to the multirotor F_{ext} that vary with position and time.

With all these considerations, the dynamic model of the VIAD-DRONE for controller derivation would result in:

$$M(\xi)\ddot{\xi} + C(\xi, \dot{\xi})\dot{\xi} + G = F_{prop}(\xi) + F_{ext} + F_{cont} \quad (16)$$

And the general expression of the attitude controller for the VIAD-DRONE will result in:

$$U_{\eta} = M_{\eta}[K_1 e_{\eta} + K_2 \dot{e}_{\eta} + K_3 \chi_{\eta} + \ddot{\eta}_d] + C_{\eta} - \tilde{\tau}_{cont} \quad (17)$$

3.6 AEROX

AEROX is an aerial robotic manipulator designed to perform physical contact inspection. It is composed of a robotic vehicle, a six-degree-of-freedom (DoF) robotic arm, and a robotic end-effector equipped with wheels and inspection sensors.

For the derivation of the dynamic model, the robotic arm attached to the aerial platform makes that the mass and inertia terms, the gravity terms and the Coriolis and centrifugal terms have a dependence on the actual values of the manipulator joints. Dynamic coupling terms with the arm joints and the attitude angles also appear, estimated by $\tilde{M}_{\eta}\ddot{\eta}$ and $\tilde{M}_{\eta\gamma}\dot{\gamma}$. Furthermore, the

contact forces F_{cont} that appear when the AEROX is pushing the end-effector against the surface it is inspecting are also considered in the model and the controller.

The aerodynamic effects of flying very close to the surfaces of the environment appear also here similarly to the VIAD-DRONE presented in the last section, making the forces and torques generated by the propellers $F_{prop}(\xi)$ varying with the relative position of the AEROX with respect to the environment. Wind will also be present, affecting its operation, generating additional forces F_{ext} on the aerial robot.

Considering all these factors, the dynamic model of the AEROX for controller derivation results in the following equation:

$$M(\xi)\ddot{\xi} + C(\xi, \dot{\xi})\dot{\xi} + G(\xi) = F_{prop}(\xi) + F_{ext} + F_{cont} \quad (18)$$

And the general expression of the attitude controller for the AEROX will result in:

$$U_\eta = M_\eta [K_1 e_\eta + K_2 \dot{e}_\eta + K_3 \chi_\eta + \ddot{\eta}_d] + C_\eta + G_\eta - \tilde{M}_{\eta\gamma} \dot{\gamma} - \tilde{M}_\eta \ddot{\eta} - \tilde{\tau}_{cont} \quad (19)$$

4. Conclusions

As the title indicates, this document presents the beta version of the advanced autonomous functionalities for aerial robots in the context of the PILOTING project. The methods and algorithms presented here still need to be integrated, tested, and validated in real experiments on the field. All this process will highlight the strong points to keep and the weak points to improve for the final version.

Regarding the localization and navigation functionalities developed within T5.1, although some preliminary tests have already been performed, they need to be thoroughly tested in real experiments first in more controlled scenarios such as low altitude viaducts or small empty tunnels. Then, they should be progressively tested and validated in even more challenging scenarios.

As for the advanced control functionalities developed within T5.3, this document presented a general modular controller architecture with specific implementations for each aerial robot, depending on the type of physical interaction with the environment. Again, the different implementations should be progressively tested and validated in real scenarios.

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